

Appendix B - PVA Demographic Parameterization

Baseline demographic input parameters in Table B.1 were derived as follows. Northern fulmars, like most tubenoses, are characterised by being long-lived with a slow, long-term monogamous breeding system producing at most a single egg each year, with low but highly variable breeding success (Mallory et al. 2020b). Ages of recruitment to the breeding population and survivorship are unknown for Canadian fulmars; therefore, these parameters were based on work from Scotland, Ireland and Alaska. Age at first reproduction was set as a fixed sex-specific variable with earlier first offspring for males than females (8 and 12 years, respectively; Dunnet 1991). This differs from Anderson et al. (2018) who set this input as 5 years for both sexes based on the earliest documented marked bird detected breeding (Dunnet 1991). Like Anderson et al. (2018), the maximum lifespan and maximum age of first reproduction were also set as fixed parameters at 50 years, based on several birds banded in Europe as breeding adults still breeding 41 years later (Dunnet 1991), and the sex ratio was assumed to be 50:50 (Mallory et al. 2020b).

The remaining demographic parameters experienced annual environmental stochasticity, such that the carrying capacity, proportion of females breeding in a given year (breeding propensity), and survival were sampled according to a mean and standard deviation in each year. Additionally, reproduction and survival were partially correlated (Environmental Variation (EV) correlation = 0.2; Anderson et al. 2018), with EV sampled from a binomial distribution, as breeding propensity (Mallory et al. 2008), breeding success (Gaston et al. 2006, Mallory et al. 2009), and adult survival (Thompson & Ollason 2001) are lowest in years with poor winter and spring conditions. The same has been documented in southern fulmars (*Fulmarus glacialisoides*; Jenouvrier et al. 2003, 2005). While Anderson et al. (2018) assumed carrying capacity was 125% of initial population size (N_0), we set carrying capacity relative to the State of Canada's Birds (SOCB) 2024 population goals for Arctic northern fulmar (Environment and Climate Change Canada and Birds Canada, 2024), because these recently devised population goals are significantly higher than 125% of our N_0 values in 2018. The SOCB 2024 goal is set at 322,698 breeding pairs, or 645,396 breeding individuals, for the entire Arctic fulmar population, while 125% of our highest 2018 total source breeding population size scenario is less than half this goal. Across our three total source population size scenarios (Table 1), the ratio of birds in BBDS:LS is near 50:50; thus we set the carrying capacity for each source population to 125% of half the SOCB 2024 goal, or 403,337 breeding individuals (996,081 total individuals including pre-breeding, extrapolated from the PVA initial stable age distribution), with a

standard deviation on the carrying capacity of $\pm 10\%$ due to environmental variation (Anderson et al. 2018).

Female breeding propensity was parameterized as 71% with high variability ($\pm 4\%$) based on the proportion of pairs at “apparently occupied sites” that laid eggs at two Canadian Arctic colonies (Prince Leopold Island and Cape Vera) from 2001-2005 (Mallory et al. 2009), in comparison to the lower value of $30 \pm 10\%$ used by Anderson et al. (2018). Anderson et al. (2018) also incorporated weak density dependence of reproductive rates by varying breeding propensity relative to density and carrying capacity. We elected to disregard density dependence as this parameterization overrides the input value of expected breeding propensity, and importantly because selection of the form of the relationship is somewhat arbitrary in the absence of detailed studies to guide this choice.

In line with Anderson et al. (2018), the mortality rate of sub-adult birds was allowed to rapidly converge with the mortality rate of adults, reaching the adult rate of 3.25% (average among early studies by Dunnet & Ollason 1978, Buckland 1982, Hatch 1987) by 3 years old, with relatively low influence of environmental variation. For many seabird species, sub-adult survival is nearly impossible to quantify due to highly delayed recruitment and natal dispersal, and this is particularly true for first-year survival, i.e. survival from fledge to one year old. In contrast to Anderson et al. (2018), we derived the parameter for mortality rate from age 0 to 1 as the inverse of the product of productivity (i.e. fledging success as the number of chicks fledged per egg laid, or survival from age 0 to fledge) and first-year survival. From Mallory et al. (2009), productivity was on average 43% but varied from 34-50% among five years at two Canadian colonies. Based on studies of southern fulmars in Antarctica, $26 \pm 15\%$ of birds marked as nearly fledging-age chicks survived until recruitment to the breeding population (Jenouvrier et al. 2005), while adult survival was on average $92 \pm 0.6\%$ (Jenouvrier et al. 2003), considerably lower than northern fulmar adult survival (96.75%, references above). Thus, we considered that northern fulmar first-year survival could range from 25-45%, and therefore derived possible values for mortality from age 0 to 1 that incorporate both productivity and first-year survival ($100\% - (43\% * \text{first-year survival})$), ranging from 80.65 - 89.25%. We conducted a sensitivity analysis to determine the influence of mortality from age 0 -1 on population growth rate (r) by running PVA models for the BBDS_{new} source population varying only the demographic parameter for age 0 to 1 mortality (based on values of first-year survival of 25-45% in 5% increments), and examining the resulting values of r under varying annual

bycatch take ranging from zero to 5,000 birds. For all PVA models with bycatch removal, we set birds to be vulnerable to bycatch mortality in their first year of life onward, where subadults (i.e. pre-breeders) and adults (i.e. breeders) are equally susceptible to bycatch mortality relative to the age distribution of the population, as Anderson et al. (2018) showed that a skewed bycatch ratio towards subadults made little impact on population trajectories due to subadults quickly taking on adult survival rates.

Our sensitivity analysis suggested that 45% first-year survival (i.e. 80.65% mortality age 0 to 1) resulted in plausible positive population growth trajectories, where r was definitively positive at zero bycatch leading to slow but steady population growth, r remained positive at relatively low levels of bycatch (100 birds taken per year), and r became slightly negative at average bycatch levels of at least 1,000 birds taken per year (Figure B.1). For all values of 0 to 1 mortality, bycatch removal of 5,000 birds led to rapid population declines (median $r < -0.22$). First-year survival of 40% or less led to negative population growth in the baseline zero bycatch model (Figure B.1). If populations would currently be experiencing naturally slower population growth rates in the absence of fisheries bycatch, then our models applying a rate of 80.65% 0 to 1 mortality would be conservative in that they would underestimate the impact of bycatch on the populations.

Table B.1. Baseline demographic input parameters used in all PVA models. Parameters influenced by stochastic environmental variation are indicated by \pm standard deviation of their input values.

Parameter	Input
Carrying capacity (breeding individuals)	403,337 \pm 10%
Reproductive system type	Long-term monogamy
Maximum lifespan	50 years
Maximum age of reproduction	50 years (both sexes)
Age at first reproduction	males: 8 years females: 12 years
Maximum clutches per year	1
Maximum progeny per clutch	1
Sex ratio at birth	50% females
Female breeding propensity	71 \pm 4%

Mortality rate from age 0 - 1 (derived as 100 - (productivity * first-year survival))	80.65 ± 5%
Mortality rate from age 1 - 2	7.5 ± 1%
Mortality rate from age 2 - 3	5 ± 0.5%
Mortality rate from age 3 and up	3.25 ± 0.05%

Figure B.1. Population growth rate (r) from PVA models under varying rates of mortality for the 0 to 1 age class and varying levels of annual bycatch removal. Median r and 95% CIs were derived for each model from the distribution of long-term r across 1,000 model iterations.

Literature Cited

- Mallory ML, Hatch S, Nettleship D. Northern Fulmar (*Fulmarus glacialis*). In: Billerman BM, editor. Birds of the World. Cornell Lab of Ornithology, Ithaca, NY, USA, 2020b.
- Dunnet GM. Population studies of the fulmar on Eynhallow, Orkney Islands. *Ibis*. 1991 Oct;133:247.
- Anderson CM, Iverson SA, Black A, Mallory ML, Hedd A, Merkel F, et al. Modelling demographic impacts of a growing Arctic fishery on a seabird population in Canada and Greenland. *Marine Environmental Research* 2018; 142: 80-90.
- Mallory ML, Akearok JA, Edwards DB, O'Donovan K, Gilbert CD. 2008. Autumn migration and wintering of northern fulmars (*Fulmarus glacialis*) from the Canadian high Arctic. *Polar Biology*, 31, pp.745-750.
- Mallory ML, Gaston AJ, Forbes MR, Gilchrist HG. Influence of weather on reproductive success of northern fulmars in the Canadian high Arctic. *Polar Biology*. 2009 Apr;32:529-38.
- Gaston AJ, Gilchrist HG, Hipfner JM. 2005. Climate change, ice conditions and reproduction in an Arctic nesting marine bird: Brunnich's guillemot (*Uria lomvia* L.). *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 74: 832-841. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2656.2005.00982.x>
- Thompson PM, Ollason JC. Lagged effects of ocean climate change on fulmar population dynamics. *Nature*. 2001 Sep 27;413(6854):417-20.
- Jenouvrier S, Barbraud C, Weimerskirch H. Effects of climate variability on the temporal population dynamics of southern fulmars. *Journal of Animal Ecology*. 2003 Jul;72(4):576-87.
- Jenouvrier S, Barbraud C, Cazelles B, Weimerskirch H. Modelling population dynamics of seabirds: importance of the effects of climate fluctuations on breeding proportions. *Oikos*. 2005 Mar;108(3):511-22.
- Dunnet GM, Ollason JC. The estimation of survival rate in the fulmar, *Fulmarus glacialis*. *The Journal of Animal Ecology*. 1978 Jun 1:507-20.
- Buckland ST. A mark-recapture survival analysis. *The Journal of Animal Ecology*. 1982 Oct 1:833-47.
- Hatch SA. Adult survival and productivity of northern fulmars in Alaska. *The Condor*. 1987 Nov 1;89(4):685-96.
- Environment and Climate Change Canada and Birds Canada. 2024. The State of Canada's Birds – Northern Fulmar. Data accessed from NatureCounts, Birds Canada. doi: TBD (will be online by late October 2024).